

D-JRP12-2.1 & 2.2: Optimised long-read sequence bioinformatics tool for the analysis of the resistome and microbial communities made publicly available.

JRP12-AMRSH5-FARMED

Responsible partner: DTU

Contributing Partners: APHA, ISS, Sciensano, UCM

GENERAL INFORMATION

European Joint Programme full title	Promoting One Health in Europe through joint actions on foodborne zoonoses, antimicrobial resistance and emerging microbiological hazards
European Joint Programme acronym	One Health EJP
Funding	This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under Grant Agreement No 773830.
Grant Agreement	Grant agreement n° 773830
Start Date	01/01/2018
Duration	60 Months

DOCUMENT MANAGEMENT

Project deliverable	D-JRP12-WP2.1 & 2.2 Optimised long-read sequence bioinformatics tool for the analysis of the resistome and microbial communities made publicly available.
Project Acronym	JRP12-AMRSH5-FARMED: Fast Antimicrobial Resistance and Mobile-Element Detection using metagenomics for animal and human on-site tests
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Other contributors	
Due month of the report	M60
Actual submission month	M60
Type <i>R: Document, report DEC: Websites, patent filings, videos, etc.; OTHER</i>	R, DEC Save date: 8-Nov-22
Dissemination level <i>PU: Public (default) CO: confidential, only for members of the consortium (including the Commission Services)</i>	PU This is the default setting. If this project deliverable should be confidential, please add justification here (may be assessed by PMT): Work from this deliverable is being prepared for publication.
Dissemination <i>Author's suggestion to inform the following possible interested parties.</i>	<p>OHEJP WP 1 <input type="checkbox"/> OHEJP WP 2 <input type="checkbox"/> OHEJP WP 3 <input checked="" type="checkbox"/></p> <p>OHEJP WP 4 <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> OHEJP WP 5 <input type="checkbox"/> OHEJP WP 6 <input type="checkbox"/></p> <p>OHEJP WP 7 <input type="checkbox"/> Project Management Team <input type="checkbox"/></p> <p>Communication Team <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Scientific Steering Board <input type="checkbox"/></p> <p>National Stakeholders/Program Owners Committee <input type="checkbox"/></p> <p>EFSA <input type="checkbox"/> ECDC <input type="checkbox"/> EEA <input type="checkbox"/> EMA <input type="checkbox"/></p> <p>FAO <input type="checkbox"/> WHO-Europe <input type="checkbox"/> OIE <input type="checkbox"/></p> <p>Other international stakeholder(s):</p> <p>Social Media:</p> <p>Other recipient(s):</p>

1. Introduction and deliverable description

Infectious disease is one of the biggest threats towards human and animal health. Infectious disease agents (mainly bacteria in FARMED focus) circulate for some time in individuals before they eventually are detected in clinical cases. Current surveillance may not reflect the true burden of infectious diseases, including antimicrobial resistance (AMR), especially if the symptoms are mild. The clinical surveillance can also be biased due to changes in the diagnostic frequency, as seen during the COVID-19 pandemic.

There is thus a need for rapid and on-site protocols for infectious bacterial disease and AMR detections where bacterial species can be identified using sequencing-based approaches. While short read sequencing methods (e.g., Illumina) are established for bacterial identifications and AMR detection in metagenomics samples (e.g., faeces and sewage) (e.g., Munk et al., 2022), their adaptability to be carried out on-site is not possible due to the lack of portability of the instrumentation, in addition to their limitations to run a real-time diagnosis. Oxford Nanopore Technology (ONT) brings a rapid and real-time diagnostic solution that provides detection, identification, and characterisation of pathogen genomes directly from metagenomic specimen using a cutting-edge 3rd generation sequencing technology (direct DNA sequencing without synthesis). Furthermore, because of the small footprint and ability to be deployed to field settings, Oxford Nanopore Technology (ONT) sequencing provides a promising next-step solution for infectious disease diagnoses (Smith et al, 2020).

Prior to evaluating the usefulness and sensitivity for ONT to detect bacterial pathogens and AMR genes from metagenomics samples in the field, there is a need to establish standards to analyse such samples in traditional lab setups (i.e., with full equipment access, electricity, and internet connection). Once those are established, on-site trials can be conducted.

D-JRP16-WP2.1 and WP2.2 that are delivered within WP2 in FARMED aimed to optimise long-read sequence analyses to identify microbial communities and AMR genes in metagenomic samples using publicly available bioinformatics tools. The main objective of WP2 was to establish best practice 'off-site' bioinformatics analyses for species and AMR detection, including optimisation of the databases used and defining KMA parameters and criteria for confidence of KMA output. This deliverable (D-JRP12-2.1+2.2), forms the methodological basis for the further use of ONT sequencing in the field (WP3). It provides, and optimises, the bioinformatics tools to align and map the generated long-read sequences (using methods elaborated in <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7429361>) to bacterial and antimicrobial resistance databases. It suggests potential parameters to call for bacterial pathogens from metagenomics samples. It also provides solutions for the bioinformatics analyses to be carried out on-site with limited or no internet connection, and without continuous supply of electricity.

2. KMA as the main aligner/mapper for AMR detection and bacterial taxonomic assignments from metagenomics samples

The KMA (k-mer alignment - Clausen et al., 2018) pipeline is implemented and used for bacterial community assignments from long-read as well as short-read sequences and was considered the standard workflow for FARMED data analysis, as it has previously been tested for Oxford Nanopore sequences and has previously been shown to outperform similar tools/methods in both accuracy and speed. KMA is an open source pipeline and can be downloaded from:

<https://bitbucket.org/genomicpidemiology/kma/src/master/>. A KMA-output wrapper is also available that facilitates compiling KMA output files into more easily interpreted tables. The wrapper is available online on: https://bitbucket.org/fremol/kma_mapstat_summary/src/master/

Initially, an online training session communicated KMA usage amongst all FARMED partners (Figure 1). During this session, the different institutes were also introduced to the KMA protocols to assign both long and short reads to bacterial taxa. This is particularly useful for standardised comparisons between both technologies across different institutes. Defined mock community (DMC) sequencing outputs (task WP1.1, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7429361>) were mapped using KMA by all partners, and all the aligned reads were assigned to bacterial taxa using the same parameters. To ensure consistency of results, initial KMA analysis was performed using all the raw sequencing data from the consortium. The entire DMC dataset, which includes the raw sequencing data files as well as the KMA output files were compiled for evaluations and comparison. This analysis aimed to evaluate the feasibility of long-read metagenome sequencing to identify pathogens.

ResFinder is compatible with both long and short reads for AMR assignments after KMA mapping, which facilitates AMR comparison of the same samples using both technologies. All the involved partners are now familiar with ResFinder and KMA pipeline for long read analyses, and DMC sequences (task WP1.1) were fed into KMA and ResFinder for AMR profiling using the same parameters. To ensure consistency of results, a single institute performed KMA analysis using all the raw sequencing data from the consortium. The entire DMC dataset, which includes the raw sequencing data files as well as the KMA output files, were compiled for evaluation and comparison. Preliminary comparison showed the top 20 most abundant bacteria in the DMC communities, which were sequenced at several institutes (<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7429361>). At this stage, the primary output to compare between partners is bacterial composition and AMR profiling. While linking genes to bacterial hosts was attempted in the lab (<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7429361>), due to the initial low ONT read output and the high computational demands for assemblies in the field, the capability of finding co-linkages of bacteria, plasmids, and AMR genes was not practicable in the field, although this remained a target for FARMED.

Figure 1. Screenshot during the online KMA training session hosted by DTU

As WP1 and WP2 are linked and based on the output from the defined microbial community analyses using Gut Microbiome Standard (GMS) bacterial mock community (Zymo) (from WP1, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7429361>), several parameters were tested within KMA to identify the bacterial species and AMR genes when spiked into complex metagenomic samples. The use of the GMS

allowed for accurate detection of the bacterial taxa and the AMR genes since the initial concentrations are known (artificial spiking).

Following several alterations, the final command, and parameters to run KMA to identify bacterial species was proposed below:

```
[kma -i input_file.fastq -o output_file -t_db FARMED_db/FARMED_db -mem_mode -bc 0.7 -bcNano -ID 0.01 -mrs 0.5 -ef -proxi 0.9 -na -nc -1t1 -ca -status -verbose 2 -t num_threads]
```

From the parameters and options recommended during the training session hosted by DTU, modifications were only brought to the minimum reads scores (-mrs) and minimum template identity (-ID) values. Various combinations of these 2 parameters were tested. Finally, the -mrs was kept to its default value (0.5) and the -ID was set to a loose threshold (0.01), with the aim to not lose too much data with a strict filtering. Therefore, the KMA output contains a lot of data for which some interpretation is needed to discriminate the true positive from the false positive, depending on the quality of their mapping scores that can be found in the resfile (.res) output of KMA (see section 4 below for further explanation). With such parameters, most of the spiked-in bacterial taxa and AMR genes were identified in the metagenomic samples with abundances that are proportional to their added concentrations in the Defined Mock Community and Gut Microbiome Standard (GMS - comprised of 21 different strains to mimic gut microbiome structure) used in the experiments of WP1 (the exceptions are mentioned below).

Amongst the undetected species, some of them were not correctly reported due to the limit of detection of the methods, while others were not detected due to an effect of the matrix, which probably affected the DNA extraction and/or the library preparation steps. Next to this, one species (*Faecalibacterium prausnitzii*) from the GMS, present at high concentration in the mix, was not properly detected (with lower mapping score than expected) because the templates belonging to this species in the database were genetically too far to have a perfect match with the GMS strain. This resulted for this species in a spread of the reads amongst the templates with each time reduced mapping score.

3. Bacterial database selection and ResFinder 4.1

Any sequence-based analysis and pipeline are reference database-dependent. Our sequence analyses, whether for bacterial taxa or AMR gene detection, are limited by which reference database is used. This issue is general for any sequencing platform generating short or long reads. This is more apparent in bacterial species assignment of the reads. The more bacterial taxa in the reference database, the more bacterial taxa we identify in our results.

Several partners have sequenced several metagenomic samples (with and without GMS community - Figure 1). At first, the reads were analysed afterwards using several bacterial databases (Figure 2) to test the accuracy of KMA at calling back the added bacterial species at abundances similar to the bacterial spiked-in proportions.

Figure 2: experimental design using the Zymo mock community

When mapping the reads using KMA to DTU genomic DB (same as DTU_db1), most of the spiked bacterial genera from the GMS were not retrieved (Figure 3), while if we attempted to retrieve the bacterial species, the output was missing 5 species (out of 21 added strains) as the reads were assigned to another congeneric species. This was also true when mapping the Illumina reads (short read sequencing), which means it is not related to ONT sequencing methods (Figure 4).

Figure 3: The identified bacterial community from 3 samples when ONT reads were mapped using KMA and DTU db1. X axis shows the sequence depth for a taxon. Y axis shows the template coverage.

Figure 4: The identified bacterial community from 3 samples when Illumina reads were mapped using KMA and DTU db1. X axis shows the sequence depth for a taxon. Y axis shows the template coverage.

The same above sequence output was then mapped with KMA and Genome Taxonomy DataBase (GDTB; <https://gtdb.ecogenomic.org/>), a publicly available database for detailed bacterial taxonomy. The outputs had a higher accuracy for calling bacterial species taxa compared to DTU_db1 (Figure 5). However, GDTB is larger in size compared to DTU_db1. The former also requires a higher computational power, which complicates in-field sequencing settings. Lastly, four bacterial species (out of 21 different strains provided in the commercial mock community) were not retrieved.

Based on the above, DTU_db1 was chosen for further improvements. Two databases were afterwards provided by DTU to be used with KMA: DTU_db1 and DTU_db2. While DTU_db1 is entirely composed of complete genome sequences, DTU_db2 contains a mix of complete genomes and genomes divided in a variable number of contigs/scaffold sequences with various lengths. Additionally, a third database, named gmstd_db, containing the exact sequence (communicated by ZymoResearch) of the bacterial species composing the Gut Microbiome Standard (GMS) used for spiking experiment (see WP1.T3) was created. The PURE sample (GMS spiked in PBS, see WP1.T3) was used to compare the 3 databases.

KMA database	Number of sequences	Genomes/ Scaffold
DTU_db1	12,335	Complete genomes
DTU_db2	19,518,663	Mix of complete genomes and scaffold
gmstd_db	15	Complete genomes of the GMS
FARMED_db	12,343	DTU_db1 + 1 missing GMS species (complete) + 2 species (scaffold)

The results showed that the composition of the database (i.e., complete genomes “DTU_db1” vs. contigs/scaffold “DTU_db2”) has an impact on the KMA results and their interpretation. When performing the analysis using the gmstd_db and DTU_db1, composed only of full genomes, all the reads belonging to a species mapped to a best hit present in the database, resulting in high mapping scores (depth, template identity and template coverage) making the result interpretation straightforward for non-expert users. On the contrary, the same analysis with DTU_db2, composed of a mix of complete genomes and contigs/scaffolds, resulted in the spread of the reads which mapped to different contigs with various mapping scores, making the interpretation more complex. Additionally, it was observed that short contigs are more prone to obtain high mapping scores because of their length. This can be misleading and inaccurate for taxonomic identification, as only a part of the genome is attributed to a species. Moreover, more false positives were reported when using the DTU_db2 in comparison with the DTU_db1. Considering all of this, a database containing mainly complete genomes, and contigs/scaffold only if complete genomes are not available, is recommended. Consequently, for the analysis of all the samples from WP1, a new database called FARMED_db was created. This FARMED_db is composed of the DTU_db1 to which was appended complete genomes belonging to *Methanobrevibacter smithii*, and contigs/scaffolds sequences belonging to *Veillonella rogosae* and *Prevotella corporis* (because no complete genome was available on NCBI for these 2 species), which were included in the gut microbial standard (GMS) bacterial composition. FARMED_db was used for any further analyses to assign bacterial species from microbiomes in FARMED.

As for AMR detection, KMA with ResFinder 4.1 (<https://cge.food.dtu.dk/services/ResFinder/>) were used. The outputs vary between the partners. For some partners all expected AMR genes were identified ,while some others did not manage to detect genes from *E. faecalis* or *S. enterica* (<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7429361>).

4. *FARMED threshold-template to call for bacterial species and ARG identification*

Next to the databases created and used in section 3 (gmstd_db and FARMED_db), a third database was created to evaluate the impact of genomes belonging to species closely related with species present in the GMS, and potentially identified as false positive. This database named gmstdFP_db is composed of the GMS genomes and the closely related genomes. From the analysis of the PURE GMS sample (<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7429361>) using the gmstd_db, gmstdFP_db and FARMED_db, the depth, template identity and template coverage values generated by KMA for each true positive and false positive species were compared to define detection threshold for species identifications. As with the loose parameters defined in section 2., a lot of data is retrieved by KMA (see report 9M-Y5), the determination of detection criteria with confidence level was needed for proper interpretation. Additionally, to consider the presence of contigs/scaffold in the database (and their impact on results interpretation as demonstrated above), the template length was included in the decision criteria to better reward the long reference templates (i.e., complete genomes). In total, 6 different levels of confidence of detection were proposed to help for data analysis. Depending on the level of detection, the taxonomic identification can be trusted (level 4 to 6) or requires a complementary analysis to confirm the result (level 2 to 3).

Although the result interpretation for ARG detection is more straightforward, a similar procedure was applied to define detection thresholds. Briefly, the sequencing data of the PURE GMS sample was processed with KMA but using the ResFinder database this time. When expected ARGs were detected, they were considered as true positives and all other detected ARG were considered as false positive. Depth and template identity values from these true and false positive were compared to elaborate thresholds for ARG detection using KMA. The criteria of template length was not included here as the ResFinder database is composed of resistance genes of comparable sizes.

5. *Adaptability to on-site trials*

In preliminary trials, the on-site sequencing and data analyses pipeline was tested in the field in February and March 2022. Samples from soil and faeces, with an addition of a single bacterial isolate from a hospital, were collected in fields. DNA extractions were done using Quick-DNA HMW MagBead Kit (D6060, Zymo Research) on BentoLab device for DNA extraction and library preparation (<https://bento.bio/devices/>) with external portable power supply. Libraries were prepared using two protocols: Rapid Sequencing Kit SQK-RAD004 on BentoLab (<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7433281>). All raw outputs (Fast5) were basecalled using an in-house built GPU-based laptop with Guppy-basecaller pipeline and high accuracy basecalling option. All resulted Fastq files were fed into KMA (after previous KMA performance assessment in WP2-T1, T2 and T3 in previous reports) for bacterial taxa and AMR identifications. From the faecal sample, approximately 65000 reads were assigned to 275 bacterial species and 12 AMR genes. As a control, *Staphylococcus aureus* bacterium was added to the faecal sample (100 µl of 10⁸ cells/mL) and *S. aureus* species was one of the abundant bacterial taxa in the microbiome analyses from the tested faeces.

An offline automated tool named “MOSS” (<https://github.com/MBHallgren/moss> - under development) to help users do read basecalling and bacterial species identification (using KMA and a

small-size bacterial database) on a GPU-based computer in the field.

Another set of tools needed for Nanopore data analysis were made available through ARIES Galaxy-based web platform (<https://w3.iss.it/site/aries/>), curated at ISS, counting about 500 users worldwide. The subscription for using ARIES is free, granting easy access to bioinformatics pipelines to users without large experience in bioinformatics analysis. In detail, the Nanoplot and Porechop tools wrappers for Galaxy systems were already available on Galaxy toolshed and were imported on ARIES and made available in the list of tools. KMA tool wrapper was also available in the Galaxy toolshed, but corrections were applied in the wrapper before importing the tool in ARIES and make it available in the list of tools. The availability of such tools on a web platform allows to perform the analyses without the need of high computer capacity on site. On the other hand, internet connection is needed for accessing it and uploading the data. Depending on the amount of sequencing data produced and on the power of internet connection, this operation could take several minutes. Once the data is uploaded, the analysis runs on ISS servers much faster than what could be achieved with on-site portable computers.

6. Comparing KMA to other tools

Two other tools for the analysis metagenomic data were compared to KMA. ONT offer a cloud-based Nextflow metagenomics analysis, Epi2Me, which offers Kraken2 and Minimap2 approaches to carry out taxonomic classification of metagenome samples. Initially the pure GMS sample sequence data was processed using the wf-metagenomics workflow using a Kraken database of capped size (PlusPF-8 – <https://benlangmead.github.io/aws-indexes/k2>). In total, 10/15 GMS species were identified by the wf-metagenomics workflow. Of the missing 5 species

- two GMS species (*Veillonella rogosae* and *Prevotella corporis*) were not in the PlusPF-8 database, however other species from the same genera were present and identified
- three GMS species were some of the lowest abundant species - *Akkermansia muciniphila* (1.5%), *Enterococcus faecalis* (0.001%) and *Clostridium perfringens* (0.0001%).

The Epi2Me workflows are that is easy to use for non-bioinformaticians as complete workflows are available via a GUI with the steps needed for taxonomy and the output is provided in html format, making it easy to use for in-experienced users as well as not requiring significant computational resources.

Kaiju is a tool used for taxonomic classification of metagenomic data, which uses a protein rather than sequence database, achieving a higher sensitivity compared with methods based on nucleotide comparison (Menzel 2016). Using the long read data, from pig and cattle farms, presented in WP1 deliverable (<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7429361>), three approaches were compared (A) KMA analysis, (B) Kaiju using raw long read data and (C) Kaiju using assembled data. An in-house analysis workflow was developed to carry out raw data processing, assembly and analysis for metagenome classification and AMR identification. Raw sample quality was checked using NanoPlot and reads were filtered using NanoFilt to remove short (<500bp) and low quality (<10) reads. The samples were then assembled using Flye, which is a de novo assembler developed for long-reads generated by PacBio and ONT (Kolmogorov et al 2020). In addition, Flye is able to carry out long-read metagenome assemblies using the metaFlye algorithm. Finally, the assemblies were taxonomically classified using Kaiju (v1.9.0) (Menzel 2016), with the RefSeq database. The RefSeq database used for Kaiju classifications was significantly bigger, harbouring 98 million sequences of archaea, bacteria and viruses, compared to the FARMED_db. Assembling the raw data improved the N50 from average of 1.4kb to 7.5kb, however there was a significant decrease in the number of bases (average 98.1%) in the assembled data compared to pre-filtered raw data. Compared to the bacterial classification of the raw data, assembling

the long read data decreased the percentage of unclassified reads from ~69% (64-74%) to ~31% (11-51%). Host (pig and/or cattle) or plant DNA were not removed from the dataset, which likely was included in a portion of these unclassified reads, which are not present in the RefSeq database, however this has not been validated yet. As well as bacterial reads, a small percentage (0.2 – 2.8%) of reads were assigned to viruses.

Sample bacterial community compositions were compared at the phyla level, which showed the number of phyla were higher in Kaiju and Epi2me outputs, which reflects the database used. *Bacteroidota*, *Firmicutes* and *Actinobacteria* were the dominant phyla by all methods (KMA, Kaiju-Raw, Kaiju-Assembled and Epi2Me methods) (cattle samples) (Figure 6). These approaches produced similar microbial profiles at the phyla level, although there were differences in the less abundant phyla, which were more likely to be picked up in the raw reads compared to the assembled data. As expected, due to KMA using a much smaller database than Kaiju or Epi2Me, KMA only identifies the most dominant microbial community members. Therefore, depending on the purpose of metagenomic analysis, a combination of raw and assembled data might need to be considered to ensure the least amount of data is lost and a true representation of the sample to be obtained.

Figure 6. Heatmap analysis of cattle microbial communities from different analysis methods. The colour intensity represents log₁₀ transformed counts of reads.

The type of database to be used was a long-standing discussion topic in the FARMED project. A huge database contains an exhaustive list of microbial entries which is beneficial when wanting to capture the true community composition and diversity. However, for in-field purposes a huge database cannot be easily accessed or utilised because of facility limitations and the time needed to complete the analysis (big databases result in longer waiting times for results as well as computational resource). In this case, a much smaller database capable of being used with limited computational resources (i.e., laptop) and requiring less time to finish analysis is a much more appealing choice, although the reference database contains much fewer and more specific entries. Therefore, there is a trade-off with

each database and what is best for the analysis, which will largely depend on the scope of the work and its aims/questions. In the FARMED project we have used both – smaller database to suit in-field work and larger database for a more in-depth analysis of the sample metagenome.

7. *Concluding remarks and FARMED recommendations*

FARMED aimed to provide and test a bioinformatic workflow to analysis long-read metagenomic sequence data, generated by the ONT MinION. We concentrated on the KMA pipeline, which is an open-source pipeline that can rapidly assign taxonomy or AMR genes to long and short read sequencing data. We deliver a set of KMA running parameters and criteria to analyse the KMA output, which were applied to other FARMED work packages (WP1- <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7429361> and WP3- <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7433281>).

Care must be taken to use a relevant database, ideally using complete genomes and avoiding contigs and scaffolds, as we found these to affect impact species identification. This was highlighted when comparing the KMA output to other metagenomics workflow, which utilise different databases as well as use the protein sequence rather than nucleotide sequence to assign taxonomy.

Long read metagenome sequencing enables the identification of host and AMR gene linkages, future work will all assess the ability to identify the linkages of AMR genes and plasmids. This will require development of database containing complete plasmids, which is likely to be large as plasmids can be highly diverse and may thus present different challenges.

During the progress of the FARMED, the ONT computational requirements changed significantly due improvements in basecalling, which is unsurprising as the technology is relatively new compared to Illumina short read sequencing. This required the implementation of a PC using graphic processing units. There are likely to be future improvements to long-read sequencing technology as well as bioinformatics tools, which require workflows to be agile and adapt to these improvements.

8. *Scientific literature*

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Advanced Research Infrastructure for Experimentation in genomicS (ARIES): a lustrum of Galaxy experience

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